

Effect of split N application on grain yield, panicle numbers, and filled grains and unfilled grains of rice.^a Pantnagar, India, 1988.

N application					Grain yield (t/ha)			Panicles/m ² (no.)			Filled grains/panicle (no.)			Unfilled grains (%)		
Basal	Tillering	6-7 DBPI ^b	Boot	Heading	N ₁₂₀	N ₁₈₀	Mean	N ₁₂₀	N ₁₈₀	Mean	N ₁₂₀	N ₁₈₀	Mean	N ₁₂₀	N ₁₈₀	Mean
1/2	1/4	1/4	–	–	6.2	6.8	6.5	184	183	184	136	132	134	11	17	14
2/3	–	1/3	–	–	6.5	6.8	6.7	182	193	188	126	125	126	20	19	20
1/5	1/5	1/5	1/5	1/5	6.9	7.9	7.4	183	197	190	147	132	140	08	12	10
1/4	1/4	1/6	1/6	1/6	6.9	7.4	7.2	191	188	190	141	134	138	10	10	10
Mean					6.6	7.2		185	190		138	131		12	15	
Treatment					LSD (0.05)			LSD (0.05)			LSD (0.05)			LSD (0.05)		
N rate					0.4			ns			ns			ns		
Time of N application					0.5			ns			ns			4		
Interaction																
N rate at same or different time of application					ns			ns			ns			ns		
Time of N application within a N rate					ns			ns			ns			ns		
CV (%) based on error b					7			7			7			28		

^ans = nonsignificant. ^bDays before panicle initiation.

Response to N application time was significant (see table). Applying N 1/5 or 1/4 as basal and 1/5 or 1/6 N

topdressed 1 wk before panicle initiation, booting, and heading increased grain yield 10%. The increase

in yield was primarily due to more filled grains per panicle. □

Effect of single superphosphate and granular superphosphate fertilizer on rice yield

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We compared response of rice to single superphosphate (SSP) (16% water soluble and 2% citric soluble P₂O₅) and granular superphosphate (GSP) (14.8% water soluble and 3.6% citric soluble P₂O₅) during 1987 wet season.

Medium-duration cultivar Kranti was transplanted 20 Jul 1987 and harvested 4 Nov 1987. Soil was medium heavy (sandy loam) with pH 6.7, 0.42% organic C, CEC 32.6 mg/100 g, and 210 kg available N, 10.5 kg available P, and 325 kg available K/ha. All treatments received 60-40-20 kg NPK/ha except that the control plot received no P. N was applied in three splits: 50% basal, 25% topdressed at tillering, and 25% at panicle initiation.

For both SSP and GSP, treatments were all P as basal, all P at tillering, and

Effect of P source on rice yield and yield attributing characters. Raipur, India, 1988.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)	Effective tillers (no.)	Panicle length (cm)
Control (no P)	2.9	3.6	3.8	14.1
GSP at transplanting	3.9	4.8	4.0	15.0
SSP at transplanting	4.8	5.9	5.6	16.2
GSP at tillering	3.7	4.6	4.0	14.3
SSP at tillering	4.3	5.2	5.0	15.8
GSP: 50% at transplanting, 50% at tillering	4.1	5.1	5.0	15.1
SSP: 50% at transplanting, 50% at tillering	5.3	6.4	5.8	17.1
LSD (0.05)	0.8	0.8	ns	

split P, 50% at transplanting and 50% at tillering.

The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications. Plot size was 144 m²; plant spacing was 20 × 20 cm.

Reduction of rice yield without any P fertilization was significant (see table). Applied as basal, SSP was much superior to GSP. Yield was significantly higher with SSP split application.

The relatively higher availability of P in water-soluble SSP might have made the difference under wetland conditions. □

Performance of *Sesbania rostrata* in acid soils

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We compared *S. rostrata*, a newly introduced green manure crop, with *S. aculeata* and *Crotalaria juncea*, green manure crops commonly grown in Kerala.

The field experiment was conducted during Jan-Mar 1988 (mean daylength 11 h 55 min) in acid soils (pH 5.0) of CSRC Karamana (11°N, 77°E and 30 m above mean sea level). The riverine alluvium, sandy clay loam soil contained 0.7% organic C and 100-7-10 ppm of available NPK with an EC of 0.3 dS/m.

The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with eight

replications. The crops were broadcast in Jan 1988 at 30 kg seed/ha. No fertilizers were applied. One irrigation was given at sowing for germination.

Plant stands were uniform in all plots. Dry matter (DM) production and N yield were estimated using standard procedures at 50, 60, and 70 d after sowing (DAS).

S. rostrata had the highest DMP and

N yields at all three growth stages. At 50, 60, and 70 DAS, *S. rostrata* produced 5.0, 6.1, and 7.3 t DM, yielding 96, 145, and 153 kg N/ha, respectively. *S. aculeata* produced 4.7, 5.9, and 6.9 t DM, yielding 85, 131, and 140 kg N. *C. juncea* produced 3.4, 5.3, and 6.3 t DM, yielding 68, 110, and 122 kg N/ha. □

Disease management

Conidia release and dispersal pattern of *Pyricularia oryzae* under cloudy or rainy conditions

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We studied conidia release patterns from discrete blast lesions during 1988 rainy season in Korea, using a KY-type spore trap. On 13-14 Jul, it rained from 12 noon to 10 a.m. Conidia were released the entire time, with two distinct peaks between 1 and 7 a.m. (Fig. 1).

The first peak, 1-3 a.m., was due to the production of conidia from pre-existing conidiophores; the second peak, at 7 a.m., was due to conidia produced from conidiophores formed since 13 Jul evening. The peaks came by chance immediately after more than 16 mm rainfall/h. More conidia were released from 7-d-old lesions.

We also observed conidia dispersal under rainy conditions 21-22 Jul, using a rotary spore trap (Fig. 2). Usually conidia dispersal during rainfall of more than 3.5 mm/h is negligible, but in this experiment conidia dispersal was observed regardless of rainfall intensity. We believe that most of the conidia released and dispersed during rainy, cloudy conditions might be important as inoculum for blast epidemics. □

1. *P. oryzae* conidia release pattern under rainy conditions in Suweon, Korea, 13-14 Jul 1988.

2. *P. oryzae* conidia and dispersal pattern in Suweon, Korea, 21-22 Jul 1988.

Yield loss due to rice blast (BI) disease at different crop stages

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In 1984, leaf and panicle BI caused by *Pyricularia oryzae* Cav. occurred extensively in Thailand. We conducted field experiments at Pathum Thani Rice Research Center during dry and wet seasons 1986 to determine rice yield loss to BI at different crop stages.

Rice variety RD23 was direct sown in an 800-m² field and 513 sample units marked by binding units of approximately 10 tillers each with a string. Infected leaf area on each sample unit was estimated 45, 60, and 75 d after sowing (DAS).

All sample units were harvested and threshed separately and grain yield adjusted to 14% moisture content.

Data for each crop stage were grouped into classes of similar disease severity levels and average severity and average yield for each group calculated (Table 1). Average yield of group 1 was used to calculate yield loss of all other groups for a particular stage. Regression analysis was conducted on these new data sets.

All three, functions presented in Table 2 show a high statistical precision. BI